

Data Set Citation

When using this data, please cite the data package

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Estudio erosión olivar Soil Olive España. Malaga
pbelart.3.1

General Information

Title:	Estudio erosión olivar Soil Olive España. Malaga
Identifier:	pbelart.3.1
Abstract:	Resultados del análisis de la erosión en suelos del olivar en dos parcelas de Antequera (Málaga)
Keywords:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ suelo○ erosión○ olivar

Involved Parties

Data Set Creators

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Associated Parties

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Organization:	Universidad de Jaén
Position:	Profesor titular
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Data Set Characteristics

Geographic Region:

Geographic Description: España, portugal, Italia, Grecia y Marruecos

Bounding Coordinates:

West: -16.375 degrees

East: 30.875 degrees

North: 45.75 degrees

South: 28.875 degrees

Time Period:

Begin: 2023-01-31

End: 2025-12-31

Sampling, Processing and Quality Control Methods

Step by Step Procedures

Step 1:

Description:

observacion directa y toma de muestras suelo

captura de 30 cm de suelo en cada punto de muestreo

Instrument(s):

pala, bascula y bolsa

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